

IHCantabria

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IH Cantabria Real time hybrid strategy in FOWT model testing

Tommaso Battistella, Albert Meseguer Urbán, Raúl Guanche García
Offshore Engineering and Ocean Energy Group

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Floating offshore wind platforms challenge

Each FOWT concept shows a **different hydrodynamic response** due to:

- Stabilization systems: semi, TLP, SPAR,...
- Mooring systems

Each wind turbine shows **specific aerodynamics and control system**.

As a general approach, in order to improve **FOWT** performance:

- **Specific control systems are needed depending on FOWT technology.**
- **Hydrodynamics vs Aerodynamics**

Floating offshore wind platforms challenge

- **Wave tank testing is a crucial step** during the development of new floating offshore wind concepts.
- Scaled prototypes are engineered to represent at laboratory scale the most important phenomena related with the **fluid-structure interaction**.
- The interaction between turbine aerodynamics and platform hydrodynamics shows important **laboratory scale effects** that need to be faced.

Floating offshore wind platforms challenge

Static lines and cables

System pulley with
suspended weights

Drag Disk

In house calibrated
multi-fan wind
generator

Wind Generator (GEVI)

Physical wind turbine for large scale testing

Multi-fan system: Software in the Loop (SIL)

The Software In the Loop (SIL), a hybrid testing strategy

The Software In the Loop method, a hybrid testing system combining, in real time, numerical and physical modelling

Aerodynamic loads calculated by means of an **UBEM model** fed with the mock up movements

Loads reproduced on the mock up by means of a six rotors **multi-fan**. The multi-fan is able to generate Thrust and Aerodynamic Moments with high fidelity.

Design valid for a range of W.T (2MW-10MW) and scales (1:50 – 1:25).

A proper calibration procedure guarantees the required loads accuracy and rate of change

Aerodynamic force calculation

UBEM model defined in prototype scale. No scaling conflict affects the calculated aerodynamic forces

Aerodynamic loads depending to:

- Wind turbine movements
Tracked by a high precision capture motion system (Qualisys®)
- Undisturbed inflow wind
Defined numerically
- Wind turbine controller
Interfaced with the UBEM model

Electronics architecture

The Loop includes a complex
electronical arrangement

Main components:

- Arduino board
- Electronic Speed Controllers
- Rotors
- Relay

The multifan evolution

Hardware

The multifan chassis is born as an ensemble of 3D-printed components and carbon fiber tubes.

Software

The definition of the aerodynamic forces were performed by look-up table relating rotor relative velocity vs Thrust and aerodynamic moment.

The multifan evolution

Hardware

Later versions were provided with an aluminium monobloc chassis

Software

The look-up table was substituted by an unsteady BEM model, allowing to improve the definition of:

- Rotor aerodynamics
- Wind turbine controller effects
- Turbulent Full-3D inflow winds

Calibration procedure

The reliability of the device is based on a strict calibration procedure

The procedure aims to define the relation between the PWMs that operate the multi-fan rotors and the generated forces. Such relation is enclosed on the **Calibration tables**.

The tolerance on the accuracy of the generated forces is set at the **3%**.

Calibration procedure

The calibration addresses also the capability to reproduce dynamic forces within the range of interest.

The multifan is undergone several trials resebling the loading paths typical of wind turbines.

Wave tank test application

Regular waves and turbulent wind

Waves

$H = 4\text{ m}$

$T = 18\text{ sec}$

Wind

$V = 11.2\text{ m/s}$

$TI = 0.20$

Wave tank test application

Thrust energy distribution

Waves: JS H 5,7 m – T 8,7 sec – G 4,7

Wind: 11 m/s Class A

Turbine: 6.2MW Machine $\Omega_{\text{rated}} = 9,9 \text{ rpm} = 0,165 \text{ Hz}$

Platform: Semi- submersible $\lambda_t = \sqrt{40} = 6.3$

Wind and Platform
modes

Waves range

3P range

Conclusions

Multi-fan system

Advantages:

- Any wind turbine can be simulated, including the control system.
- The whole thrust curve can be properly reproduced, including the negative aerodynamic damping region
- Turbulent wind series can be simulated
- The gyroscopic loads can be also simulated.
- The multi-fan system allows to change the testing scale in order to achieve the maximum performance of the tests campaign.

Disadvantages:

- Complex mechanical and electronic system
- Labour-Intensive calibration process
- Power supply: extra-cables

Future developments

- Capability to generate Thrust along with the Moments around three axes
- Involvement of yaw control
- Compatibility with comercial servo-aero modules
- Wireless data communication

Complex Loading Demonstration NREL 5MW, mean wind speed 10 m/s shear vertical profile 0.14

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Regular Wave (FIH15-00029-C2-RW-H4p0-T18p0-WDT11p2-ABS-00): H = 4 (m) // T = 18 (sc) // Dir = 0 deg (prototype) // Wind = 11.2(m/s)
Surge Acceleration: Nacelle

Surge: ACCELERATION STATISTICS:

-Mean = 0
-STD = 0.203

Significant Surge (m/s²)
-Significant Peak Value (A^{+1/3}) = 0.464
-Significant Trough Value (A^{-1/3}) = -0.458

Maximum Surge (m/s²)
-Maximum Peak Value (A^{*}) = 0.84
-Minimum Trough Value (A^{*}) = -0.792